

Preliminary Investigation of Intra Pin Burnup Distribution Challenges and Potential Mitigation Strategies for LEU+ Fuel Cycle

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ABSTRACT

The commercial nuclear power industry pursues extended 24-month cycles and power uprates resulting in higher fuel burnup. Increased burnup exacerbates the radial burnup peaking at the fuel pin outer region and causes severe localized fuel degradation. Mitigating this spatial effect is crucial for safe extended operation. This study explores strategies to flatten the radial burnup distribution in PWRs using pin- and assembly-level simulations. The investigation focused on three main goals: (1) Understanding of homogeneous fuel compositions and sensitivity analysis effect on localized burnup, (2) implementation of duplex fuel designs and (3) exploring use of homogeneous Thorium Oxide (ThO_2) as a substitute for burnable poisons (BPs). The study concludes that combining a duplex fuel structure to flatten the spatial burnup with homogeneous thorium to manage reactivity and minimize BP usage is a promising strategy to flatten local burnup peaking.

Keywords: Burnup, Thorium, PWR, Serpent

1. INTRODUCTION

The commercial nuclear power industry's push to extend cycle length from 18 to 24 months is motivated by achieving possible economic benefits due to reduced number of outages and related costs [1]. In order to achieve longer cycle length, approval is being sought for increased allowable fuel rod burnup limits from 62 MWd/kgU to 75 or 80 MWd/kgU [2]. As fuel burnup increases, the radial burnup distribution within a fuel pin becomes more pronounced going over 1.5 times the relative average fuel pin burnup at proposed EOL [3]. The effect of burnup on fuel performance is well-known, resulting in fuel degradation effects on fuel thermal and structural properties [4,5]. To extend cycle length of commercial reactors to 24 months, the spatial burnup effects will likely need to be properly mitigated. Advances in accident tolerant fuel include efforts made to support higher burnup and enrichment [6,7]. Reducing the spatial effect of burnup and exploring methods of flattening the burnup distribution could lead to even longer cycle lengths by evening out the fuel degradation throughout the fuel pin rather than highly localized on the outer edge/rim.

The use of thorium in PWR fuel assemblies has been previously explored and has shown promise as a method of BOL reactivity control and flattening power peaking [8]. Also previously explored was the use of the duplex fuel design with a pure Thorium Oxide (ThO_2) outer annular region [9]. This study sought to consider the effects on Thorium in two parts: Effect on radial burnup distribution and

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assessing the ability to integrate Thorium in a UO_2 matrix as a burnable poison for reactivity control purposes.

All simulation results of this study were generated from the Serpent Monte Carlo code. The traditional PWR fuel pin geometry [10], with dimensions given in Table I, and 17x17 PWR assembly were modeled using an octant symmetry. Fuel pin radial burnup distribution was captured using 15 equal volume annular regions; the fuel pin had a PWR standard radius with a reflective boundary condition and radially discretized into 15 equal volume annular regions to capture the average burnup of each region.

Table I. Fuel pin main parameters

Parameter	Value, cm
UO_2 Fuel Radius	0.39218
Helium Gap Radius	0.40005
Zirconium cladding Radius	0.45720
Light water square cell half-length	0.63000

2. METHODOLOGICAL SENSITIVITY STUDIES

To understand the radial burnup distribution effects from fuel composition and geometry, homogenous mixed UO_2 fuel with burnable poisons and ThO_2 , altering fuel radius, and the addition of a pure ThO_2 external fuel layer were considered and presented in Sections 2.1 and 2.2. Next, the effects of a linear enrichment gradient were explored in Section 2.2. The promising results of the enrichment gradient lead to the development of a duplex fuel design that was partially optimized and explored in Section 2.3. Finally, an assembly-level analysis was performed, and results are presented in Section 2.4 for the best performing case duplex fuel design. Using a non-linear reactivity model, an equivalent-performing core was determined with 10% ThO_2 homogeneously-mixed fuel and using the duplex fuel design.

2.1. HOMOGENEOUS FUELS

As the burnup limit is increased, the observed radial burnup distribution mean value increased and the maximum burnup experienced at the edge of the fuel pin further worsened, as shown in Figure 1(a). The outer region localized burnup drastically increases with overall burnup, as shown in Figure 1(b).

Figure 1. Radial Burnup Distribution (a) comparison between LEU and LEU+ fuel at respective EOL Burnup and (b) radial burnup time evolution for 6.7% LEU+ fuel

With the goal of mitigating localized burnup effect, the use of burnable poisons and thorium was explored. Fuel pin models were developed using homogeneously mixed burnable poisons and ThO₂, all mixed with 6.7% enriched UO₂ fuel, and are summarized in Table II. It was previously determined that an enrichment of approximately ~6.2% would be sufficient fissile material to extend cycle lengths to 24 months [10].

Table II. Homogeneously Mixed Fuel Pin Compositions

Burnable Poisons		Thorium Oxide		Ternary Mixtures			
Nat. ErO ₂	5 wt%	ThO ₂	10 wt%	Nat. ErO ₂	5 wt%	+ThO ₂	5 wt%
	10 wt%						15 wt%
GdO ₂	5 wt%		20 wt%	GdO ₂	5 wt%	+ThO ₂	5 wt%
	10 wt%						15 wt%
HfO ₂	5 wt%		HfO ₂	5 wt%	+ThO ₂	5 wt%	
	10 wt%					15 wt%	

The use of burnable poisons alone resulted in a peakier burnup distribution with the outer edge burnup increasing with larger poison additions. In contrast, the use of Thorium showed a slight decrease. These results are shown in Figure 2, with Gadolinium producing the highest maximum burnup increase. Considering the effect on criticality due to a Thorium addition, Figure 3 shows that mixing Thorium reduces the initial fissile loading. For a 10wt% ThO₂ mixture, the criticality at 65 MWd/kgU has a significant drop of approximately 0.025 (2,500 pcm) whereas at 80 MWd/kgU the criticality almost reaches that of pure UO₂ fuel.

Figure 2. Effect of binary and ternary fuel compositions on relative fuel pin outer edge burnup

Figure 3. Effect of Thorium on fuel pin criticality

2.2. ENRICHMENT AND GEOMETRIC SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

The effect of applying a linear enrichment gradient over 15 equal volume annular regions was explored while maintaining a 6.7% enrichment overall. A gradient with lower enrichment in the center and higher enrichment at the edge resulted in worse performance with higher edge burnup and worsened self-shielding effects. Another gradient with higher enrichment in the center and lower enrichment at the periphery showed a promising burnup distribution flattening effect. The 4.9% enrichment case in the most center region was identified as the "flattest". This linear gradient variation was acknowledged as not practical for manufacturing – the key focus was on the phenomena behavior at a limit.

Two other sensitivity analysis were conducted by altering the fuel pin radius and the effect of the addition of a pure ThO_2 exterior wrapper layer. Changing the fuel pin radius by +20% and -20% was found to have a marginal to no effect on the relative burnup distribution. Adding an external layer of ThO_2 (resulting in a 10 wt% or 20 wt% overall fuel composition) did not change the magnitude of the peak burnup but shifted the maximum closer to the pin's center.

2.3. DUPLEX FUEL DESIGN AND ANALYSIS

As a practical implementation to an enrichment gradient concept, a duplex fuel design with a central pin region and a single outer annulus was tested. This design significantly flattens the burnup distribution and is more practical for potential manufacturing. Preliminary testing involved testing nine combinations of volume ratios ($VR = \frac{V_{inner}}{V_{outer}}$) of 1/3, 1, 3 and enrichment ratio ($ER = \frac{E_{inner}}{E_{outer}}$) of 1.5, 1.75, 2.5. The most promising duplex configuration was VR of 3 and ER of 2.5, tested with both 0% and 10% ThO_2 , shown in Figure 4. In both cases of with and without Th, the maximum radial burnup was reduced by approximately 20%. The addition of Thorium does not worsen the duplex design's burnup distribution.

Figure 4. Duplex fuel relative radial burnup at constant volume ratio $V_r = 3$ and varying enrichment ratio E_r for (a) 0wt% Th and (b) 10wt% Th

3. FUEL ASSEMBLY ANALYSIS

The analysis was extended to the fuel assembly level, where the radial pin burnup issue was further worsened. The overall fuel assembly burnup was captured at 62 MWd/kgU for a 'base case' of 6.2% enrichment, standard design fuel pins with 24 BP pins at 8wt%, no Thorium, and 93 Fresh Fuel Assemblies (presented in Figure 7(a-b)) with the maximum burnup exceeding an additional 54% of the assembly average burnup.

Using a nonlinear reactivity model and assuming a core leakage of 3%, 2- to 3-batch core behavior was approximated. The poisoned assemblies reactivity were modeled for burnups up to 80 MWd/kg and fit with a 4th-order polynomial described in Eq. (1):

$$\rho(BU) = a_0 + a_1BU + \dots + a_4BU^4 \quad (1)$$

The core reactivity was obtained using a weighted average of assembly reactivities, at their respective burnups (for Fresh Fuel, Once-Burned, Twice-Burned assemblies), described in Eq. (2):

$$\rho_{core}(BU) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} N_i \rho(BU + iB_{cycle}) - \rho_L \quad (2)$$

Where N_i is the number of fuel assemblies for batch i , $N = \sum N_i$, and ρ_L is the assumed core leakage. Assuming equal power share among fuel batches, batch cycle length B_{cycle} was found with Eq. (3):

$$\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N N_i \rho(iB_{cycle}) = \rho_L \quad (3)$$

With a constant BP loading pattern with 24 BP pins and with 10 wt% ThO₂, the enrichment (6.20, 6.45, 6.70, 6.95, 7.20%), Gd poison loading (3.0, 5.0, 7.0, 8.0, 9.0wt%), and fresh fuel assemblies (65 to 113 in increments of 4) were varied to find an equivalent core reactivity to the base case. Figure 5 partially shows this search process. The observed trend in cycle length as a function of fresh fuel assemblies requires more exploration in a full-core level analysis – assumptions about equal power sharing may need to be addressed. Interpolation was required to achieve target values of 62 MWd/kgU burnup and 24 month cycle length (CL). The closest equivalent core was found (see Figure 6) to rely on 6.78% enrichment, 4.5 wt% Gd in BP pins, and 93 fresh fuel assemblies (Relative difference in CL was 1.385%).

Equivalence is achieved by minimizing the total squared error between the core reactivity (as a function of burnup) of the new configuration and the base case. The addition of Thorium resulted in a 56% Reduction of BP loading with no observed significant effect on radial burnup distribution. Less aggressive use of BP will lead to more efficient thermal management in the fuel assembly and less power peaking.

Figure 5. Fuel Assembly (a) cycle length and (b) discharge burnup at varying enrichments with 24 BP pins at 5.0 wt% Gd as a function of number of fresh fuel assemblies

Figure 6. Equivalent case core (6.78% enrichment, 4.5wt% BP pins, 10wt% ThO₂, and 93 Fresh Fuel Assemblies) that best matches the base case (6.2% enrichment, 8wt% BP pins, 0wt% ThO₂, and 93 Fresh Fuel Assemblies) performance

Figure 7. Comparison of fuel assembly burnup performance for (a) base case maximum pin burnup (b) base case average pin burnup (c) equivalent case duplex fuel maximum pin burnup and (d) equivalent case duplex fuel average pin burnup

Implementation of a duplex fuel design on all pins in an assembly using the best test configuration ($VR = 3, ER = 2.5$ with Table III giving the design specifications) at the equivalent case presented above (6.78% Enrichment, 24 BP with 4.5% Gd, Th 10%) resulted in 23.67% reduction of maximum relative pin burnup (from 1.5408 to 1.1761). Figure 7 shows the large reduction in maximum burnup and no observable strong effect on the average burnup.

Table III. Equivalent Duplex Fuel Specifications

Region	Radius	Enrichment
Inner	0.3396	7.88%
Outer	0.3922	3.15%

4. CONCLUSIONS

The study concluded that as cycle lengths are extended, the dramatic increase in burnup at the fuel pin edge can be mitigated with two promising strategies identified. Duplex fuel using regions of different enrichments can significantly flatten the spatial burnup distribution. The addition of homogeneous Thorium can help manage core reactivity and minimize the use of burnable poisons, which negatively

impact the burnup profile due to power peaking within the core and reduces the residual Gd impact on fuel cycles.

Results demonstrate that while conventional burnable poisons (BP) worsen the burnup peak, the addition of homogeneous ThO₂ slightly decreased the maximum burnup at the fuel edge. A 10 wt% homogeneous ThO₂-mixed fuel achieved equivalent core reactivity performance with a 56% reduction in BP loading. A duplex fuel design (utilizing a higher enrichment center and lower enrichment annulus) proved highly effective in reducing the maximum relative pin burnup by 23.67% at the assembly level. This study also confirmed that the addition of 10 wt% ThO₂ did not impede the duplex design's burnup flattening capabilities.

Future work should include a full-core level analysis to capture the burnup profiles of the highest-power pins. Further exploration is needed to find optimal duplex fuel configurations, to properly consider manufacturing limitations and costs, and to estimate fuel cycle cost impacts.

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